

THE CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES OF SCHOOL ABANDONMENT AND EVASION

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Abstract:

This work aims to present an analysis of the causes and consequences of school abandonment and dropout, the main factors that contribute to this problem, and how it can influence the future of these students. The research and data analysis was carried out in a public institution, the Centro de Ensino Professor Nonato Sampaio school, in Coelho Neto Maranhão, in September 2022. In this context, meetings were held with teachers in order to get to know, discuss and analyze actions of overcoming the problem of truancy at the Nonato Sampaio Education Center school. It is worth mentioning that a bibliographical research was carried out to analyze the year 2021. The research aims to seek a better delimitation of the main causes of school dropout and dropout, thus detailing the reasons identified as motivating this problem. A statistical survey of the data was carried out, first citing generally and then searching for relevant information about the causes.

Key Words: *School dropout, dropout, student.*

I. Introduction

School dropout is a persistent problem in Brazilian public schools. It is known that there are laws ensuring students' access and permanence in this environment. The Federal Constitution of 1988, in its Article 205, states that education is a right for all, as does the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LDB) No. 9.394/1996, which regulates educational norms. Today, more than ever, we see the importance of discussing the theme of "school dropout and abandonment." This issue caught our attention, especially since we experienced some dropouts at the beginning of our course, which saddened us because we knew our colleagues were being forced to leave due to circumstances beyond their control—dreams were being cut short and annulled.

The topic of school dropout and abandonment generates many studies and reflections, aiming to find the most plausible ways to minimize or even eradicate this issue that affects all levels of education. School dropout has been a significant problem in Brazilian education, seemingly difficult to solve, and each year, the dropout rates rise alarmingly, worsening the situation. Factors such as drugs, repeated failures, alcoholism, school location, vandalism, and a lack of values and preparation for the workforce can be decisive when students decide whether to stay in or leave school.

Ferreira and Veloso (2003) indicate that in Brazil, the level of education among individuals shows a high degree of persistence across generations. That is, individuals with more educated parents tend to have a significantly higher average level of education than those whose parents had lower educational attainment, indicating limited educational mobility. This reflects the social, economic, and cultural nature of the school dropout issue.

It is important to emphasize that there are numerous causes leading students to abandon their studies, which can be linked to both internal and external factors. Internal factors, as understood by schools, include unqualified teachers who provide poor quality education, leading to student repetition and dropout, as well as a lack of educational materials. External factors include social inequality, neglect and lack of encouragement from parents or guardians, student disinterest, and the responsibility to contribute to family income, among others. According to Bossa (2007), dropout is closely tied to academic failure, which is not a natural phenomenon but rather a result of the interaction between teaching proposals, student learning absorption, teaching and evaluation models, as well as the school and family contexts.

It is noteworthy that teachers have reported that, in most cases, parents are unaware of their children's abandonment of studies. This is due to a lack of monitoring and concern for their children's future. The participation of parents in their children's education is crucial. Article 229 of the Federal Constitution of 1998 states that "parents have the duty to assist, raise, and educate their children."

In light of these problems, an analysis was conducted on issues related to school abandonment, aiming to demonstrate the dropout rates at the Centro de Ensino Professor Antônio Nonato Sampaio in Coelho Neto, Maranhão, and to present the main causes of this abandonment. This analysis was necessary to evaluate the data regarding dropout rates in this institution, which required conducting both bibliographic and field research to better delineate the main causes of school dropout and abandonment. Subsequently, a statistical survey was carried out regarding dropout rates in the mentioned institution, first in general terms and then seeking information from official data available from the institution. From the analysis of this data, the problem was identified along with the need for planning to diagnose the situation of school dropout, highlighting that the school should organize more strategies to confront this issue.

Material And Methods

In the course of the research, it was presented to us that we must understand the existence of school abandonment and school evasion. School abandonment is characterized when a student stops attending classes during the school year, while school evasion occurs when a student, regardless of being approved or disapproved, does not enroll or re-enroll to continue their studies. School evasion is a fact that has always been and continues to be present in Brazilian education, and we need to take into account and try to understand the factors that lead these students to abandon their studies. According to Oliveira:

"School abandonment is composed of the combination of various dimensions that integrate and conflict within this problematic. These dimensions are of a political, economic, cultural, and social nature. Thus, school abandonment cannot be understood or analyzed in isolation. This is because socioeconomic, cultural, educational, historical, and social dimensions, among others, mutually influence each other" (OLIVEIRA, 2009, p. 4).

In this sense, the authors point out that the reasons leading to school evasion are much more complex, as it is necessary to understand the entire context behind each abandonment. Understanding the daily lives of these young students is essential for a deeper analysis of the facts and for seeking solutions to reintegrate these young people into the school environment.

Causes and consequences of school evasion can be considered an age-old problem in Brazilian schools. Therefore, it is necessary to delve deeper into understanding the causes behind this issue. Oliveira states:

"The insertion of young people into the job market becomes a continuous demand, and these young adults are called upon early, considering their financial restrictions to enter this world. Many of them try to balance study and work in the hope of obtaining a better job and, consequently, higher wages. However, physical exhaustion and work demands, among other reasons, strongly influence the decision to abandon school" (OLIVEIRA, 2009, p. 13).

From the perspective of other authors, young people have the illusion that they can balance study and work, but they encounter a reality that is entirely different from what they imagined, leading them to ultimately abandon their studies. The lack of concentration and fatigue results in low academic performance for these students. The

financial aspect is a priority for these young individuals, as many need to contribute to the family income. According to Dias:

"The lack of employment and low family income, the lack of motivation from parents and the students themselves, and early pregnancy have been cited as some of the reasons that lead students to abandon their studies. External reasons include family demotivation; many parents are complicit in their children's dropout by not providing any support to continue studying and claiming that their children will not be able to support the family if they do not work with them" (DIAS, 2013, p. 33).

According to Dias (2013), from the perspective of other authors, young people have the illusion that they can balance study and work, but they face a reality that is completely opposite to what they imagined, leading them to abandon their studies. The lack of concentration and fatigue result in low academic performance, and the financial focus is predominant among these young individuals, as many of them need to help with family income.

II. Result

The research sample is limited to 03 (three) educators: 1 (one) General Manager, 1 (one) Deputy Manager, and 1 (one) Pedagogical Coordinator, who represent 100% of the total staff involved in the school's management. The managers are aged between 35 and 59 years. All hold a full degree; the General Manager has a degree in Portuguese Language, the Deputy Manager in Biological Sciences, and the Pedagogical Coordinator in Mathematics and Pedagogy. They have all passed public service exams and have over 15 years of teaching experience.

A pre-prepared questionnaire was used, containing open and closed questions about the subjects and the topic in question. It was administered to 03 (three) Managers at the Professor Antônio Nonato Sampaio Teaching Center, located at Rua Dr. Paulo Ramos, S/N Centro, 65620-000 - Coelho Neto – Maranhão, Brazil. The managers oversee the morning, afternoon, and evening shifts.

Data analysis was conducted based on the factors derived from the questionnaire responses, which were selected in order of relevance concerning the causes and consequences of school abandonment and evasion.

3.1 Data Analysis and Interpretation of the Research

To maintain confidentiality, the managers are identified as G1, G2, and G3. Below is the manager's understanding of the causes and consequences of school abandonment and evasion at the Professor Antônio Nonato Sampaio Teaching Center in Coelho Neto, Maranhão. The first question was: "What was the number of students enrolled in 2021 from the 1st to the 3rd year of high school at the school?" In response to this question, the following result was obtained: The number of students enrolled in 2021 was 881.

Gráfico 01

The second question was, “What was the number of APPROVED students in 2021 from the 1st to the 3rd year of high school at the school?” The interviewee responded as follows:

The number of approved students in 2021 was 808. According to the interviewee, this was a very positive number considering the pandemic that affected the world.

The third question was: “What was the number of DROPOUT students in 2021 from the 1st to the 3rd year of high school at the school?” The following result was obtained:

The number of students who dropped out in 2021 was 12. The interviewee stated that the school, in light of this situation, conducts active searches to bring students back to the school environment, providing support to ensure they do not abandon school again.

The fourth question was, “What was the number of failed students in 2021 from the 1st to the 3rd year of high school at the school?” The interviewee responded as follows:

The number of failed students in 2021 was 61. The interviewee reported that this number of failures was due in some cases to a lack of parental support, early pregnancy, involvement with alcohol or drugs, and the need to work to help support the family.

The fourth closed question directed at the manager was, “In your opinion, is there motivation or interest from the school community and the state itself in clarifying or conducting a diagnosis regarding the causes of evasion?” In response to this question, the following result was obtained:

The manager indicated that the school community cares for its students and is sensitive to the increase in school evasion. Active searches included interviews with families to identify the causes of this evasion. Once identified, projects were developed within the school environment to encourage these students to return.

The fifth closed question directed at the manager was, “Select the options that best characterize the difficulties in the teaching-learning process for acquiring reading and writing satisfactorily, as they are problems of order,” and the following response was obtained:

(G1): The need to enter the job market early; students have to abandon their studies to dedicate time to work in order to help cover household expenses.

(G2): The need to enter the job market early; students have to abandon their studies to dedicate time to work in order to help cover household expenses.

(G3): It can be stated that one of the factors contributing to school evasion is the situation of female students who have small children and either have no one to leave them with or cannot afford to pay someone to take care of their children while they go to school to study.

The sixth question was, “Does the Department of Education and the Regional Superintendency of Education to which the school is linked establish joint actions to combat evasion?” In response to this question, the following answer was obtained:

The interviewee responded that, yes, the Department of Education establishes actions to combat school evasion. When the pedagogical team is unsuccessful in their efforts, the Department of Education proposes other means to try to bring the student back to the school environment.

The seventh question was, “Are there research projects or plans to combat evasion involving social protection network facilities such as CRAS (Social Assistance Reference Center), CREAS (Specialized Social Assistance Reference Center), bodies like the Guardianship Council and the Public Ministry, in addition to the State Department of Education?” In response to this question, the following answer was obtained:

(G1): Yes. The active search involves various stakeholders; the Guardianship Council is a permanent and autonomous body, non-judicial, responsible for ensuring compliance with the rights of children and adolescents as defined in Law 8.069/90. Article 56 of the Statute of the Child and Adolescent (ECA) assigns the leaders of elementary and early childhood education institutions the duty to report cases of frequent unexcused absences, school evasion, and failure to the Guardianship Council. When the Guardianship Council is informed, it activates the protection network.

(G2): Did not respond.

(G3): Did not respond.

III. Conclusion

The theme of “school evasion and abandonment” was chosen because it is a source of concern for all the academics involved in this article. It has been observed that this issue is far from being resolved, as it affects various

levels of education in both public and private institutions. A change is necessary; public policies must be implemented to alleviate the causes that exacerbate this problem and reduce school evasion and abandonment.

It was noted that family mediation is crucial when a student shows interest in leaving the institution before completing their course. It becomes essential for educators to use their methodologies in a way that teaches beyond what is necessary for completing education. At the end of this research, it was possible to determine that external factors influence whether a student remains in school, but internal factors are also highly relevant.

The conclusion of the research on school evasion and abandonment reveals the complexity of this problem, which transcends the walls of educational institutions. Although external factors, such as socioeconomic conditions and lack of infrastructure in schools, play a significant role in student retention, internal factors cannot be underestimated. Aspects such as the student's relationship with their family, the school environment, and the teaching methodology adopted are crucial determinants. Family mediation, for example, stands out as an essential factor: when parents or guardians actively engage in their children's school life, the likelihood of abandonment decreases significantly.

Moreover, the role of educators is fundamental. It is imperative that teachers not only transmit content but also create a welcoming and stimulating learning environment where students feel valued and motivated to remain in school.

Additionally, effective public policies must be implemented not only to address external causes but also to strengthen interpersonal relationships and the educational experience. This includes training for educators, psychological support programs, and activities that promote student engagement with the school community.

Therefore, to mitigate school evasion and abandonment, a joint effort is necessary that considers both internal and external factors. Only in this way can we build a more inclusive and effective educational system that promotes student retention until they complete their courses. Education is a fundamental right and must be accessible to all, as it is the key to a more just and equal future.

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